

Multi-Time-Scale Analytical Modeling of Large-Scale AI Model Training Power Dynamics and Its Impact on Grid Stability

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Abstract—Large-scale data centers consume vast amounts of electrical energy during both the training and inference phases of AI models, yet their load characteristics differ fundamentally. Inference loads are predictable as they directly correlate with user activity patterns, while AI model training processes exhibit intense multi-timescale power fluctuations, ranging from millisecond-level compute-communication alternations to hourly-scale training phase transitions. The frequency and amplitude of these fluctuations depend heavily on training strategies, parallel configurations, and hardware platform architecture. According to North American Electric Reliability Corporation’s Characteristics and Risks of Emerging Large Loads report, such dynamic behavior can trigger extreme load change rates (dP/dt) in data centers, posing challenges to grid stability. To precisely quantify this impact, this paper proposes an analytical simulation framework that explicitly models the power load dynamics of data centers during AI model training. By computationally analyzing forward/backward propagation times, communication latency, and checkpoint I/O overhead, integrated with GPU utilization and peak power characteristics, simulations cover diverse hardware platforms and network topologies of data centers, coupling both grid-following and grid-forming inverters. The study systematically evaluates dynamic security risks under varying training configurations and energy structures within large-scale grid simulations.

Index Terms—AI model training, power dynamics, grid stability, grid-following, grid-forming

I. INTRODUCTION

The rapid growth of artificial intelligence (AI) workloads has fundamentally transformed data center power demand characteristics. Unlike traditional computing facilities with relatively smooth load profiles, AI data centers (AIDCs) driven by thousands of synchronized Graphics Processing Units (GPU) exhibit severe transient power fluctuations and significant step-load changes [1]–[4]. Modern GPU clusters can experience power swings from 20% to over 100% of rated capacity within milliseconds, creating unprecedented challenges for both facility infrastructure and utility grid stability.

According to North American Electric Reliability Corporation’s report on emerging large loads, such dynamic behavior can trigger extreme load change rates (dP/dt) that exceed typical grid protection thresholds [1]. For a typical AI training

cluster, observed dP/dt values can reach several hundred MW/s during synchronized phase transitions, posing significant risks to grid frequency stability and requiring careful coordination between data center operators and grid planners.

This paper makes two primary contributions. First, a simplified analytical framework for modeling multi-timescale power dynamics during AI model training is presented, validated against published training runs. Second, a four-bus power system model is developed to analyze the interaction between AIDC loads and hybrid inverter-based resources, specifically examining the stability implications of grid-forming (GFM) rated power sizing under various grid connection scenarios.

II. AI TRAINING POWER MODELING

Unlike inference workloads that follow predictable user activity patterns, AI model training exhibits intense power fluctuations at multiple timescales [5]. The training process comprises distinct computational phases, forward propagation, backward propagation, gradient synchronization, and periodic checkpointing. Each with characteristic power consumption. During compute phases, GPU power approaches thermal design power (TDP), while communication and I/O phases see significant power drops. The synchronized behavior of thousands of GPUs creates extreme load dynamics that differ fundamentally from traditional data center workloads.

A. Multi-Timescale Power Dynamics

AI model training exhibits power fluctuations across multiple timescales [5]:

L1 – Micro Scale (ms): Forward and backward propagation phases alternate within each micro-batch. Forward pass duration is determined by computational load and GPU efficiency.

L2 – Batch Scale (100ms–1s): After gradient computation, GPUs synchronize via Ring AllReduce, during which compute cores idle and power drops to 30–40% of peak [6].

L3 – Phase Scale (minutes): Periodic checkpoint saves create “power valleys” as data transfers from GPU to storage [7], [8].

L4 – Macro Scale (hours): System-level events such as fault-induced restarts, cold-start inrush currents, or mainte-

nance windows introduce additional power dynamics at longer timescales.

B. Simulation Architecture and Workflow

To accurately model these multi-timescale dynamics, an analytical simulation framework is developed as illustrated in Fig. 1. The simulation uses an analytical approach rather than discrete-event simulation, enabling efficient computation of power profiles for clusters with thousands of GPUs. The simulation workflow proceeds in five steps:

Step 1: Time Discretization. The simulation divides the training duration into millisecond-level time steps.

Step 2: Phase Identification. For each time step, the simulator determines the active training phase (Forward, Backward, AllReduce, or Checkpoint) based on the batch schedule and pipeline configuration. The hierarchical approach identifies L1 micro-scale phases within each micro-batch, L2 batch-scale communication phases, and L3 phase-scale checkpoint events. Different phases map to different utilization levels: Forward/Backward phases operate at 90–100% TDP, AllReduce drops to 30–40%, and Checkpoint phases reach near-idle power.

Step 3: Power Assignment. Once the phase is determined, instantaneous power is computed using a physics-based model that accounts for GPU dynamic voltage and frequency scaling behavior [9].

Step 4: Cluster Aggregation. Individual GPU power values are summed across the cluster based on the parallelism strategy. In Synchronous mode, all pipeline stages execute the same phase simultaneously, producing sharp transitions. In Pipeline One-Forward-One-Backward (1F1B) mode, stages are offset in time, requiring weighted aggregation across staggered stages [5].

Step 5: Facility-Level Aggregation and Filtering. The macro-scale events (L4) such as fault-induced restarts can be injected. Finally, the cluster power is multiplied by Power Usage Effectiveness (PUE) to represent the total facility interconnection power demand. Additionally, to reflect the physical response of power supply units and transformers, a low-pass filter is applied to the aggregated power profile

C. Pipeline Scheduling Impact

Pipeline scheduling strategies significantly affect aggregate power dynamics [5]. Fig. 2 shows the Synchronous mode where all pipeline stages execute the same phase simultaneously. This mode creates sharp power transitions with $|dP/dt|$ reaching approximately 100 - 200 MW/s, which aligns with field cases reported in [1]. Fig. 3 shows the 1F1B Staggered mode where stages are offset in time, reducing maximum dP/dt to about 64 MW/s while maintaining similar average power.

In Synchronous mode (Fig. 2), all pipeline stages execute simultaneously, creating sharp transitions. Color-coded regions show distinct training phases: forward/backward propagation (90–100% TDP), AllReduce communication (30–40% TDP valleys), and checkpoint I/O (deepest drops to near-idle).

Fig. 1. Simulation Architecture: Five-step analytical power modeling workflow, from time discretization and hierarchical phase determination (L1–L3) to power assignment, cluster aggregation, and facility-level filtering (L4 + PUE).

Fig. 2. Power profile of LLaMA-3.1-405B training (16,000 H100 GPUs) in Synchronous mode. Sharp transitions cause $|dP/dt|$ peaks in the range of 100–200 MW/s.

The red dotted line represents the average load power (14.3 MW). Power swings between 15.4 MW (peak) and 3.4 MW (minimum) generate significant load ramps.

In 1F1B mode (Fig. 3), offset pipeline stages create a “sliding window” effect. While peak power remains comparable at 15.3 MW, minimum rises to 4.5 MW (some GPUs always computing, supplemented by continuous cooling and auxiliary loads). Maximum $|dP/dt|$ drops significantly to 64 MW/s.

The dP/dt histograms reveal fundamentally different statistics. Synchronous mode (Fig. 2) exhibits a heavy-tailed distribution. Notably, the rapid load drops during checkpoint initiation drive distinct negative dP/dt spikes extending into the -100 to -200 MW/s range. In contrast, 1F1B (Fig. 3) shows a concentrated unimodal distribution with significantly reduced tails, transforming behavior from intermittent shocks to continuous moderate fluctuations compatible with grid frequency regulation.

Staggering acts as a smoothing filter, preserving total energy while drastically changing transient characteristics. For clusters exceeding 10,000 GPUs, 1F1B is essential to avoid triggering grid protection or requiring expensive conditioning equipment. The negative dP/dt events are particularly relevant for Section IV’s GFM sizing analysis, determining power absorption requirements during load valleys.

Fig. 3. Power profile in 1F1B Staggered mode. Pipeline staggering reduces $|dP/dt|$ to approximately 64 MW/s while maintaining similar energy consumption.

D. Validation Against Published Training Runs

The simulation framework is validated against reported metrics from four major training runs in the literature. Since most references do not provide dP/dt data or detailed power curves, three metrics are evaluated: total energy consumption, training time, and average power. The results are summarized in Table I.

TABLE I
VALIDATION RESULTS: SIMULATION VS. LITERATURE

Model	Energy (Sim/Lit)	Time (Sim/Lit)	Power/GPU (Sim/Lit)
GPT-3 [3], [5], [10]	1324/1287 MWh +2.9%	34.7/34 d +2.1%	281/270 W +4.2%
LLaMA [4]	21.3/21.6 GWh -1.4%	82.3/80 d +2.9%	645/700* W -7.8%
BLOOM [11]	430/433 MWh -0.7%	126/118 d** +6.4%	369/400* W -7.7%
DeepSeek [12]	2.05/2.00 GWh +2.6%	63.1/54 d** +16.9%	646/700* W -7.7%

*Est. from TDP; **Ignores HW overheads.

Total energy deviations remain within $\pm 3\%$ for most cases (GPT-3: +2.9%, LLaMA: -1.4%). Larger time deviations for BLOOM (6.4%) and DeepSeek-V3 (16.9%) stem from

unmodeled hardware overheads such as memory fragmentation and network congestion. The 7–8% lower per-GPU power versus nominal TDP reflects realistic communication and checkpoint states, validating the framework for grid planning studies where detailed power curves are needed but measurements are unavailable.

III. FOUR-BUS GRID MODEL

The proposed model represents a typical medium-voltage (10 kV) microgrid hosting a medium-sized AIDC [13], [14]. The load profile follows the dynamics described in Section II-C, with its average power serving as the per-unit base.

As illustrated in Fig. 4, the four-bus system comprises: Bus 1 serves as the point of common coupling (PCC) to the utility grid, which is modeled as a weak grid with a Short Circuit Ratio (SCR) of 2, providing voltage and frequency reference during grid-connected operation; Bus 2 hosts the AIDC load connected via a 1 km line with its characteristic high dP/dt profile described in Section II; Bus 4 represents a renewable energy power plant (photovoltaic or wind) equipped with grid-following (GFL) inverters connected via a 7 km line, which serves as the primary power source for the AIDC; Bus 3 hosts a battery energy storage system (BESS) with grid-forming (GFM) capability connected via a 2 km line, functioning as a power buffer to mitigate the impact of load fluctuations on the grid, or as a backup power source during islanded operation when switch S_1 is open.

Fig. 4. Four-bus system topology with GFM (energy storage), GFL (PV), AIDC load, and optional slack bus (grid connection).

A. Grid-Following Converter Model

The GFL converter is modeled as a controlled current source synchronized to the grid via a Phase-Locked Loop (PLL) [15]. The output current is controlled in the dq -frame:

$$I_{\text{GFL}} = (I_d + jI_q)e^{j\theta_{\text{PLL}}} \quad (1)$$

where θ_{PLL} is the internal phase angle of the GFL, governed by PLL dynamics. f-P and U-Q droop controllers modify the current references based on frequency and voltage deviations.

B. Grid-Forming Converter Model

Following the equivalent modeling methodology in [16], the GFM converter's inner-loop control and current limiting behavior can be represented by an equivalent circuit. During the transient to sub-transient timescale following disturbances, the internal voltage phasor \underline{e}^* from the outer power loop is assumed constant, and the GFM's response is dominated by its inner-loop control. As illustrated in Fig. 4, the GFM can be modeled as an internal voltage source \underline{e}^* behind an equivalent impedance $\underline{Z}_{\text{eq}}$. When the output current amplitude $|\underline{i}|$ remains below the current threshold I_{th} , the equivalent impedance is zero, and the point-of-connection (POC) voltage \underline{u} equals the internal voltage \underline{e}^* . However, when $|\underline{i}|$ exceeds I_{th} , the current limiting strategy activates and inserts a non-zero equivalent impedance between \underline{e}^* and \underline{u} :

$$\underline{u} = \underline{e}^* - \underline{Z}_{\text{eq}} \cdot \underline{i} \quad (2)$$

The magnitude of $\underline{Z}_{\text{eq}}$ is determined by the current limiting strategy to enforce $|\underline{i}| \leq I_{\text{th}}$. For a given grid impedance \underline{Z}_g and fault voltage \underline{v}_f , the output current is:

$$\underline{i} = \frac{\underline{e}^* - \underline{v}_f}{\underline{Z}_{\text{eq}} + \underline{Z}_g} \quad (3)$$

By setting $|\underline{i}| = I_{\text{th}}$, the required equivalent impedance can be solved. This equivalent impedance representation captures the essential behavior of various current limiting strategies: when current limiting activates, the GFM transitions from ideal voltage-source behavior ($\underline{Z}_{\text{eq}} = 0$) to current-limited behavior ($\underline{Z}_{\text{eq}} > 0$), fundamentally altering its dynamic interaction with the grid.

C. Heterogeneous-Converter Grid Model

The network equations couple GFM, GFL, and load buses through admittance matrix Y [17]:

$$I = Y \cdot V \quad (4)$$

The AIDC load is modeled as time-varying conductance $G_L(t) = P_{\text{load}}(t)/|V_L|^2$, where $P_{\text{load}}(t)$ follows the training power profile from Section II. The slack bus provides infinite-bus voltage reference when grid-connected, or is disabled for islanded operation.

IV. CASE STUDIES

Three configurations are analyzed using the Synchronous mode power profile (A representative 20-second window of LLaMA-3.1-405B training) from Fig. 2 as the AIDC load input, representing the most demanding scenario with extreme dP/dt transients. While the framework covers L1–L4 timescales, these studies focus on critical L1–L3 dynamics (milliseconds to minutes) for converter stability, excluding L4 system-level events (e.g., fault/restart) which require broader coordination.

A. Case 1: Islanded Configuration

In the islanded configuration (slack bus disabled, S_1 open), the renewable generation (GFL) operates at rated power with constant output, while the GFM dynamically supplies or absorbs the power difference between the GFL output and the time-varying AIDC load. To ensure reliable operation during nighttime or periods when the GFL is unavailable, the GFM must be capable of supplying the full AIDC load independently. Therefore, the GFM rated power is set to 1.0 p.u. with a current threshold $I_{th} = 1.2$ p.u. to handle the maximum load demand. The GFL operates at 1.0 p.u. representing full renewable output, and the AIDC average load is 1.0 p.u.

Fig. 5 shows that when the AIDC load drops rapidly during AllReduce or checkpoint phases, the excess power from the GFL must be absorbed by the GFM. The GFM operates as a bidirectional power buffer: during load peaks, it supplements the GFL output; during load valleys, it absorbs the surplus generation.

Fig. 5. Case 1: Islanded operation. Top: Active power (Load in green, GFM in red, GFL in blue). Bottom: Current magnitudes. The GFM absorbs excess power during load drops.

B. Case 2: Grid-Connected with Under-rated GFM

In grid-connected mode (S_1 closed), the renewable generation (GFL) continues to operate at rated power with constant output, while both the utility grid and the GFM share the responsibility of balancing the power difference with the AIDC load. Since the grid can absorb or supply significant power, the GFM capacity requirement is reduced compared to islanded operation. According to industry recommendations, 20–30% GFM capacity relative to load rating is typically sufficient for peak shaving applications [1]. In this case, a GFM capacity of 30% of the average AIDC load, with $I_{th} = 0.3 \times 1.2 = 0.36$ p.u. The GFL rated power is 1.0 p.u.,

and the AIDC average load is 1.0 p.u.. During the first 10 seconds of Fig. 6, the GFM successfully buffers L1–L2 level fluctuations (forward/backward propagation and AllReduce phases), maintaining nearly constant grid power (purple line) despite high-frequency AIDC variations. This demonstrates effective decoupling of sub-second training dynamics from the utility grid.

However, when L3-level checkpoint events occur, a critical instability emerges. The sustained power imbalance drives the GFM current beyond I_{th} , activating current limiting via virtual impedance insertion. This transitions the GFM from ideal voltage-source behavior to current-limited operation, fundamentally altering the system's equilibrium structure. As analyzed in [17], the GFM loses its continuously existing stable equilibrium manifold at this operating point. Consequently, perturbations propagate to the GFL through PLL dynamics, triggering coupled oscillations between the two converters. This instability is exacerbated by the weak grid condition in this configuration.

Fig. 6. Case 2: Grid-connected with under-rated GFM (0.3 p.u.). Top: Active power (Load in green, GFM in red, GFL in blue, Grid in purple). Bottom: Current magnitudes. Current limiter activation triggers coupled oscillations.

C. Case 3: Grid-Connected with Adequately-rated GFM

The GFM rated power is raised to 50% of the average AIDC load, with $I_{th} = 0.5 \times 1.2 = 0.6$ p.u., while other parameters remain unchanged. Fig. 7 demonstrates stable operation with the GFM operating within its linear region, avoiding current limiter activation. While the GFM successfully suppresses L1–L2 level fluctuations, it cannot fully decouple L3-level checkpoint events from the grid.

This limitation arises from impedance-based power sharing between the GFM and the grid. Since the GFL operates in constant-power mode while both the GFM and grid act as voltage sources, power fluctuations are distributed according to

the inverse ratio of their equivalent impedances. As indicated in Fig. 4, the GFM is located 2 km from the PCC while the grid connection has an equivalent impedance corresponding to SCR=2, resulting in $Z_{\text{Grid}}/Z_{\text{GFM}} \approx 3.5$. Consequently, approximately 78% of the power fluctuation is absorbed by the GFM while 22% propagates to the grid, a ratio consistent with the simulation results in Fig. 7. This represents a fundamental topological constraint: with finite line impedances, complete decoupling requires minimizing Z_{GFM} (siting storage closer to the PCC).

Fig. 7. Case 3: Grid-connected with adequately-rated GFM (0.5 p.u.). Top: Active power (Load in green, GFM in red, GFL in blue, Grid in purple). Bottom: Current magnitudes. Sufficient overcurrent capability ensures stability.

V. CONCLUSION

This paper analyzed the multi-timescale power dynamics of AI model training and their impact on grid stability through a four-bus power system simulation. Key findings and recommendations include:

- **Training Scheduling:** Pipeline scheduling strategies like 1F1B can reduce extreme dP/dt events by over 70% compared to synchronized operation. This software-level mitigation complements hardware solutions and should be considered in coordinated data center-grid planning.
- **GFM Sizing:** The conventional 20–30% GFM sizing for peak shaving is insufficient for AIDC dynamic stability due to current limiter-induced oscillations with GFL sources. A GFM capacity $\geq 50\%$ of the average AIDC load is recommended to ensure operation within the linear region. This requirement becomes increasingly critical as grid impedance rises.
- **GFM Siting:** Power fluctuation sharing between the GFM and the grid follows the inverse impedance ratio. To maximize the buffering effect and minimize grid-side

power variations, the GFM should be sited as electrically close to the PCC as possible, minimizing the effective impedance between the storage system and the point of common coupling.

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